

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1935	Ciriaco Morón Arroyo	1957	1962	2002		Spanish philologist	
1935	Merid Wolde Aregay	1957	1971	2005		Ethiopian historian and a scholar of Ethiopian studies	1935-2008
1935	Kay Williamson	1957	1964	2000	w	British linguist ("mother" of Nigerian linguistics)	1935-2005
1935	Leonid Rudnytzky	1959	1965			Ukrainian linguist, professor of German, Slavic and Ukrainian Studies	
1935	Samuel Jay Keyser	1960	1962	1998		American theoretical linguist (history and structure of the English language and on linguistic approaches to literary criticism)	
1935	Rolf Wilhelm Brednich	1960	1960	2000		German Europeanist ethnologist and ethnographer (Volkskundler) and folklorist	
1935	Andrey Zaliznyak	1961	1965	2017		Russian linguist, an expert in historical linguistics, dialectology and grammar	1935-2017
1935	Mary Lefkowitz	1961	1961	2005	w	American scholar of Classics	
1935	James M. Redfield	1961	1961	2016		American the Edward Olson Distinguished Service Professor of Classics	
1935	Ulrich Schindel	1961	1961	2003		German classical philologist	
1935	Margaret M Manion	1962	1972	2007	w	Australian art historian and curator (scholarship on the art of the illuminated manuscript)	
1935	Colin Robert Chase	1962	1971	1984		American associate professor of English	1935-1984
1935	Léon Pressouyre	1962		1997		French historian of medieval art	1935-2009
1935	Pratapaditya Pal	1962	1962	1995		Indian scholar of Southeast Asian and Himalayan art and culture, specializing particularly in the history of art of India, Nepal and Tibet	
1935	Mikhail Gasparov	1963	1963	2005		Russian philologist and translator	1935-2005
1935	Herbert Ernst Brekle	1963	1963	2001		German typographer and linguist	1935-2018
1935	Barbara Myerhoff	1963	1968	1980	w	American anthropologist and filmmaker, and founder of the Center for Visual Anthropology	1935-1985
1935	Alan Blum	1964	1964	2015		Canadian professor of sociology (Culture of Cities Centre)	
1935	Peter W. Nesselroth	1964	1968	1998		American Professor emeritus of French and Comparative Literature	
1935	Фрізман Леонід Генріхович	1964	1967	2009		Ukrainian literary scholar, educator	1935-2018

1935 Klaus Kohler	1964	1964	2002	German phonetician	
1935 Myrna Gopnik	1964		2002 w	Canadian Professor Emerita of Linguistics, researcher on the KE family, an English family with several members affected by specific language impairment	
1935 Janez Orešnik	1965	1965	2004	Slovenian linguist (comparative linguistics)	
1935 Николаев Геннадий Алексеевич	1965	1965		Russian linguist (Theory and history of Russian and Slavic word formation; the history of the Russian literary language, the scientific heritage of the Kazan Linguistic School (KLSH))	
1935 Henry Widdowson	1965	1973	2005	British linguist and an authority in the field of applied linguistics and language teaching	
1935 David McKnight	1965	1977	1997	Canadian-British anthropologist and ethnographer who specialized in the anthropology of Australian aborigines	1935-2006
1935 Roger Keesing	1965	1965	1993	New Zealand linguist and anthropologist, most notable for his fieldwork on the Kwaio people of Malaita in the Solomon Islands, and his writings on a wide range of topics including kinship, religion, politics, history, cognitive anthropology and language	1935-1993
1935 Harvey Sacks	1966	1966	1975	American sociologist (ethnomethodology tradition)	1935-1975
1935 Karl G. Heider	1966	1966	2008	American visual anthropologist	
1935 Adrienne L. Kaeppler	1967	1967	2006 w	American anthropologist, curator of Oceanic Ethnology at the National Museum of Natural History	
1935 Donatien Laurent	1967	1974	2002	French musicologist and linguist	1935-2020
1935 Eva Hajičová	1968	1968	2006 w	Czech linguist	
1935 Taddesse Tamrat	1968	1968	2000	Ethiopian historian and scholar of Ethiopian studies	1935-2013
1935 Dariush Shayegan	1968	1968	2017	Iranian the most consequential thinkers of contemporary Iran and the Near East	1935-2018
1935 Maria Eugenia Bozzoli	1968	1975	1992 w	Costa Rican anthropologist, sociologist and human rights activist, the country's first woman anthropologist	
1935 Jane Hubert	1968		2002 w	British social anthropologist, known in particular for her work in mental health and intellectual disability	1935-2019
1935 Svitlana Shvachko	1969	1971	w	Ukrainian linguist	
1935 Jay Ruby	1969	1969	2003	American scholar who was a professor in the Department of Anthropology at Temple University	

1935	Shamsur Rahman Faruqi	1969		1994	Indian poet and an Urdu critic and theorist	
1935	Simon Leys	1970	1970	1994	Belgian-Australian writer, essayist and literary critic, translator, art historian, sinologist, and university professor	
1935	Daniel L. Overmyer	1971	1971	2001	Canadian Professor Emeritus in the Department of Asian Studies and the Centre for Chinese Research	
1935	Ibrahim Krzović	1974	1974	2008	Bosnian Art historian and art critic	
1935	Niels Ingwersen	1974		2003	Danish scholar in Scandinavian Studies	
1935	Sandra Noll Hammond	1974		2009 w	American dancer, teacher, dance historian, and educator	
1935	Michael Peyron	1975	1975	1998	French-British specialist in the field of Berber language, literature and culture	
1936	Richard Douglas Lane	1957	1957	2002	American scholar, author, collector, and dealer of Japanese art	1936-2002
1936	Jean Canavaggio	1958		2001	French biographer and former emeritus professor of Spanish literature	
1936	Louie Crew	1959	1971	2002	American professor, successful campaign for the acceptance of gay and lesbian people by Christians in general, and the Episcopal Church in particular	1936-2019
1936	Euan MacKie	1959	1959	1998	British archaeologist and anthropologist, prominent figure in the field of Archaeoastronomy	
1936	Harlan Lane	1960	1960	2012	American psychologist (speech, Deaf culture, sign language)	1936-2019
1936	Paul Postal	1960	1963	2001	American linguist	
1936	William Calin	1960	1960	2002	American senior scholar of Medieval French literature and French Poetry	1936-2018
1936	George Cardona	1960	1960		American linguist, Indologist, Sanskritist, and scholar of Pāṇini	
1936	Frank Otto	1960	1960	2006	American educator, pioneer in computer-assisted language learning (CALL), entrepreneur, and the founding executive director of CALICO (the Computer-Assisted Language Instruction Consortium)	1936-2017
1936	Éva Pócs	1960	1982	2008 w	Hungarian ethnographer and folklorist	
1936	Donald Clarence Laycock	1959	1962	1988	Australian linguist and anthropologist (languages of Papua New Guinea)	1936-1988

1936	F. James Rohlf	1961	1962	2018	American Anthropologist (biological statistics)	
1936	Finn-Erik Vinje	1961	1961	2006	Norwegian philologist	
1936	Don D. Fowler	1961	1965	2003	American anthropologist and archeologist	
1936	Charles Segal	1961	1961	2002	American classicist renowned for his application of critical theory to ancient texts	1936-2002
1936	Henry Mayr-Harting	1961	1961	2003	British medieval ecclesiastical historian	
1936	Eugene N. Lane	1962	1962	2000	American classical philologist and archaeologist	1936-2007
1936	Dong Jian	1962		2011	Chinese literary scholar who specialized in the history of the theatre of China	1936-2019
1936	Judith Lynne Hanna	1962	1976	2011 w	American anthropologist, scholar, and author	
1936	Glen Bowersock	1962	1962	2006	American historian of ancient Greece, Rome and the Near East	
1936	Geoffrey Neil Leech	1963	1968	1996	British specialist in English language and linguistics	1936-2014
1936	Грищенко Арнольд	1963	1963	2006	Soviet-Ukrainian linguist	1936-2006
1936	Zinka Zorko	1963	1986	2003 w	Slovenian linguist and academic	1936-2019
1936	Doris Debenjak	1963		1991 w	Slovenian Slovene and Gottschee German linguist and translator	1936-2013
1936	Richard H. Cracroft	1963	1970	2001	American author and emeritus professor of English	1936-2012
1936	Heinz Jurgen Wolf	1963	1967	2001	German linguist	1936-2016
1936	Nelson H. H. Graburn	1963	1963	2006	British-American Professor Emeritus in Sociocultural Anthropology	
1936	J. P. Gumbert	1964	1972	2003	Dutch academic who specialised in medieval European manuscripts	1936-2016
1936	Olga F. Linares	1964	1964	2008 w	Panamanian–American academic anthropologist and archaeologist, and senior staff scientist (emerita)	1936-2014
1936	Bernard Saladin D'Anglure	1964	1971	2001	Canadian anthropologist and ethnographer (innovative methodology and elaboration of the concept of the "third sex")	
1936	Rodmonga Potapova	1965	1965	w	Russian computational linguist	
1936	Nancy Dorian	1965	1965	2003 w	American linguist	
1936	Jerry Lee Norman	1965	1969	1996	American sinologist and linguist	1936-2012
1936	Shire Jaamac Axmed	1965		2001	Somali-Swedish linguist notable for his contribution to the creation of the modern Latin script for transcribing the Somali language	
1936	Marcio Veloz Maggiolo	1965	1970	1996	Dominican writer, archaeologist and anthropologist	

1936	Johan Sundberg	1966	1966	2001	Swedish Professor of Music Acoustics	
1936	Thomas Givon	1966	1969	2005	Israeli-American linguist and writer, one of the founders of "West Coast Functionalism"	
1936	Breandán Ó Buachalla	1966		1995	Irish scholar of the Irish language	1936-2010
1936	Маркович Владимир Маркович	1966	1966	1996	Russian literary critic, specialist in Russian literature of the 19th century, in particular in the work of I. S. Turgenev	1936-2016
1936	James C. Faris	1966	1966	1995	American anthropologist and epistemologist	
1936	Johnnetta Cole	1967	1967	2017 w	American (Afro-) anthropologist, educator, museum director, and college president	
1936	Moshe Shokeid	1968	1968	2013	Israeli prominent social anthropologist specializing in American and Israeli studies	
1936	James M. Freeman	1968	1968	2000	American anthropologist	
1936	Harold M. Ross	1968	1970	2010	American cultural anthropologist who studied the Baegu community and culture on the island of Malaita in the Solomon Islands	
1936	T. F. Chen	1968		2001	Taiwanese painter, art historian, writer, and philosopher	
1936	A Cruttenden	1969	1974	2001	British Emeritus Professor of Phonetics	
1936	Jan Brøgger	1969	1970	2006	Norwegian professor of social anthropology and a clinical psychologist	1936-2006
1936	Cato Wadel	1969	1972	2005	Norwegian social anthropologist.	1936-2011
1936	Carol Duncan	1969	1969	2005 w	American Marxist-feminist scholar known as a pioneer of 'new art history', a social-political approach to art, who is recognized for her work in the field of Museum Studies, particularly her inquiries into the role that museums play in defining cultural identity	
1936	Suzette Haden Elgin	1970	1973	1980 w	American researcher in experimental linguistics, construction and evolution of languages and poetry and science fiction writer	
1936	Мартыненко Григорий Яковлевич	1971	1972		Russian Professor of Department of Mathematical Linguistics, singer, lyric-dramatic tenor, soloist of the Petersburg concert, writer	
1936	Paul Li	1971		2006	Taiwanese linguist	
1936	Burton Hatlen	1971	1973	1999	American literary scholar and professor	

1936	Guy Achard	1972	1979	2002	French Latinist and historian of Ancient Rome	
1936	Alleen Pace Nilsen	1973	1973	2011	American literary scholar, linguist, and one of the pioneers of both humor studies and children's literature studies	
1936	Rita P. Wright	1973	1984	2017 w	American anthropologist	
1936	Margaret Lock	1976	1976	2001 w	British-Canadian medical anthropologist, known for her publications in connection with an anthropology of the body and embodiment, comparative epistemologies of medical knowledge and practice, and the global impact of emerging biomedical technologies	
1936	Jean Berlie	1983	1985	2011	French socio-anthropologist specialising in Asia and China former Naval Aviation pilot	
1936	Jean-Paul Savignac	1983			French translator of Latin, Greek, and Gaulish	
1937	Anna Morpurgo Davies	1958	1960	2004 w	Italian philologist (comparative Indo-European linguistics)	1937-2014
1937	Norbert Miller	1959		2006	German scholar of literature and art	
1937	Terrence Kaufman	1960	1963	2005	American linguist (documentation of unwritten languages, lexicography, Mesoamerican historical linguistics and language contact phenomena)	
1937	James L. Guetti	1960	1964	2000	American Professor of English at Rutgers University, philosopher of language, author	1937-2007
1937	Emanuel Schegloff	1961	1967	2002	American Distinguished Professor of Sociology, the creator of the field of Conversation Analysis	
1937	Anatoly Khazanov	1961	1966	2017	Russian-American anthropologist and historian	
1937	Martin Litchfield West	1961	1965	2004	British philologist and classical scholar	1937-2015
1937	Stanley Insler	1962	1962	2012	American Emeritus Professor of Sanskrit and Comparative Philology	1937-2019
1937	Paul Gerhard Schmidt	1962	1962	2000	German medievalist and professor emeritus of medieval Latin philology	1937-2010
1937	Boris Uspensky	1962	1964		Russian linguist, philologist, semiotician, historian of culture	
1937	Ahmad Tafazzoli	1962	1966	1997	Iranian Iranist and professor of ancient Iranian languages and culture	1937-1997
1937	Lionel Tiger	1962	1962	2010	Canadian-American anthropologist	
1937	Henri Wittmann	1963		2001	Canadian (Quebec) linguist	

1937 Anatoly Liberman	1963	1965	2002	Russian linguist, medievalist, etymologist, poet, translator of poetry and literary	
1937 Geir Kjetsaa	1963	1963	2004 w	Norwegian professor in Russian literary history, translator of Russian literature, and author of several biographies of classical Russian writers	1937-2008
1937 Rodney Huddleston	1963	1963	2002	British linguist and grammarian	
1937 Anoop Chandola	1963	1965	2003	Indian-American linguist-anthropologist, originally from Pauri	
1937 Gerald Graff	1963	1963	2008	American professor of English and Education	
1937 Michel Peissel	1963	1964	2000	French ethnologist, explorer and author	1937-2011
1937 Kenneth Maddock	1963	1969	1995	Australian eminent anthropologist in Australia, and respected, rigorous scholar of Australian Aboriginal societies	1937-2003
1937 Oladele Awobuluyi	1964	1967	2009	Nigerian linguist and author	
1937 Paul Newman	1964	1967	2005	American linguist (Hausa language of Nigeria and Chadic language family)	
1937 Azartash Azarnoush	1964	1964	2004	Iranian linguist	
1937 Barbara Aland	1964	1964	2002 w	German Professor of New Testament Research and Church History	
1937 Herbert Schutz	1965	1968	2003	German-Canadian philologist (Germanic and Slavic Studies/Modern Languages)	1937-2018
1937 Peter Edgerly Firchow	1965	1965	2008	American literary scholar and educator	1937-2008
1937 Johannes Fabian	1965	1969	2002	German professor of Anthropology	
1937 Richard Borshay Lee	1965	1965	2002	Canadian anthropologist	
1937 Marjorie Halpin	1965	1973	2000 w	American-Canadian anthropologist best known for her work on Northwest Coast art and culture, especially the Tsimshian and Gitksan peoples	1937-2000
1937 Bruce Rigsby	1965	1965	2002	American-Australian anthropologist specializing in the languages and ethnography of native peoples on both continents	
1937 James Peacock	1965	1965	2015	American anthropologist	
1937 Erich Segal	1965	1965	2010	American author, screenwriter, educator and classicist	1937-2010
1937 Peter von Matt	1965	1965	2002	Swiss philologist and author	
1937 James Matisoff	1966	1967	2002	American linguist (Tibeto-Burman languages, phonology)	

1937 Robert Hetzron	1966	1966	1997	Hungarian-American linguist (comparative study of Afro-Asiatic languages)	1937-1997
1937 Larry Selinker	1966	1966	1993	American linguist (second-language acquisition)	
1937 Gerard Béhague	1966	1966	2005	Franco-American thnomicologist and professor of Latin American music	1937-2005
1937 E. P. Sander	1966	1966	2005	American New Testament scholar and a principal proponent of the "New Perspective on Paul"	
1937 David Roberts	1966	1968	2004	Australian professor of German studies	
1937 Matti Rissanen	1967	1967	2007	Finnish researcher in English linguistics (a pioneer in English historical corpus linguistics)	1937-2018
1937 Otto Schaden	1967	1977	2000	American Egyptologist	1937-2015
1937 Diana Greenway	1967		2003 w	British historian and academic, who specialised in medieval history and palaeography	
1937 William Ross Maples	1967	1967	1997	American noted forensic anthropologist working at the C.A. Pound Human Identification Laboratory at the Florida Museum of Natural History	1937-1997
1937 Robert Lawless	1967	1975	2012	American cultural anthropologist	1937-2012
1937 Allan H Pasco	1968	1968	2016	American the Hall Distinguished Professor of Nineteenth-Century Literature	
1937 Leonard Talmy	1968	1972	2005	American professor of linguistics and philosophy	
1937 Richard Gombrich	1968	1970	2004	British Indologist and scholar of Sanskrit, Pāli, and Buddhist Studies	
1937 Alla Ter-Sarkisants	1968	1968	2007 w	Russian Armenian historian and ethnographer	1937-2019
1937 Richard Werbner	1968	1968	2004	American anthropologist who specializes in the Zimbabwe and Botswana region, including ritual, personal and historical narrative, politics, law, regional analysis	
1937 Gerd Simon	1968	1968	2002	German Germanist and linguist	
1937 Burghard B. Rieger	1969	1969	2002	German computational linguist	
1937 Elisabeth Gülich	1969	1969	2014 w	German linguist	
1937 Mall Hiimäe	1969	1983	2013	Estonian folklorist-ethnologist	
1937 David Adams Leeming	1969	1970	2007	American philologist, Professor Emeritus of English and Comparative Literature	

1937	Larry Gene Heien	1969	1969	1991	American linguist, Slavist, expert of Russian studies and Russian language teaching, also known for his interest in music	1937-1991
1937	Lisa Block de Behar	1969	1984	2011 w	Uruguayan professor of Linguistics and researcher in Literary Theory, Comparative Literature and Communication media	
1937	Tina Howe	1969	1969	2015 w	American playwright	
1937	Ksenia Kepping	1969	1969	2002 w	Russian Tangutologist, known principally for her study of Tangut (or Mi-nia) grammar	1937-2002
1937	Robert S. P. Beekes	1969	1969	1997	Dutch linguist who was emeritus professor of Comparative Indo-European Linguistics	1937-2017
1937	Ofer Bar-Yosef	1970	1970	2013	Israeli archaeologist and anthropologist whose main field of study was the Palaeolithic period	
1937	Karol Daniel Kadłubiec	1970		2004	Polish ethnographer, folklorist and historian from the Zaolzie region of the Czech Republic	
1937	Mary Garrard	1970	1970	2006 w	American art historian and emerita professor, "one of the founders of feminist art theory"	
1937	Brigitte Jordan	1971	1978	2012 w	German-American professor, scientist, and consultant who was described as the midwife to the "Anthropology of Birth"	
1937	Yeda Pessoa de Castro	1974	1974	2000 w	Brazilian ethnolinguist (anthropologist and linguist)	
1937	Jim Reed	1974		2004	British scholar of German literature	
1937	Anna Blume	1993	1997	w	German Professor of the History of Art (Photography)	
1937	John A. Saliba	1976		2007	Maltese-American Jesuit priest , a professor of religious studies at the University of Detroit Mercy and a noted writer and researcher in the field of new religious movements	
1937	María Concepción García Gainza	1976		2001 w	Spanish art historian, educator and writer	
1937	Narasingha Sil	1978	1978	2011	Indian-American professor of European and English history (religion)	
1938	Niara Sudarkasa	1959	1964	2007 w	American (Afro) scholar, educator, Africanist and anthropologist	1938-2019
1938	Ross Saunders	1961	1970	2003	American Professor Emeritus of Linguistics	1938-2005
1938	Willem J.M. Levelt	1961	1965	2006	Dutch psycholinguist	

1938	Diane Barwick	1961	1964	1986 w	Canadian-Australian anthropologist, historian, and Aboriginal-rights activist	1938-1986
1938	Nico H.J. van den Boogaard	1962	1969	1982	Dutch medievalist scholar, professor	1938-1982
1938	Paul Wexler	1962	1967	2014	American-Israeli linguist	
1938	Norbertas Vėlius	1963		1996	Lithuanian folklorist specializing in the Lithuanian mythology	1938-1996
1938	James D. McCawley	1963	1965	1999	British (Scottish)-American linguist	1938-1999
1938	Anna Wierzbicka	1964	1964	2015 w	Polish linguist (semantics, pragmatics)	
1938	Jerzy Bańcerowski	1964	1964	2008	Polish professor of philological sciences	
1938	Alan Cameron	1964	1964	2008	British classical philologist, ancient historian and Byzantine	1938-2017
1938	Helmut Satzinger	1964	1964	2003	Austrian Egyptologist and Coptologist	
1938	John R. Ross	1965	1967	2006	American poet and linguist	
1938	Reinhard Hartmann	1965	1965	2001	Austrian lexicographer and applied linguist	
1938	Robert Beard	1965	1966	2000	American linguist	
1938	Zygmunt Frajzyngier	1965	1968	2004	Polish Linguist	
1938	Albert Hauf	1965	1976	2007	Spanish (Majorcan) philologist, literature historian and literary critic	
1938	Paz Battaner	1965	1973	w	Spanish philologist and lexicographer	
1938	John Laver	1965	1975	2004	British phonetician	
1938	Marron Curtis Fort	1965	1965	2003	American-German linguist and professor (study of Saterland Frisian language and Low German (plattdeutsch))	1938-2019
1938	Bram Dijkstra	1965		2000	American professor of English literature	
1938	Jane Marcus	1965	1973	2003 w	American pioneering feminist literary scholar working in the fields of feminist theory, gender studies, modernism, and women's history	1938-2015
1938	Gernot Ludwig Windfuhr	1965	1965	2009	German professor of Department of Near Eastern Studies	
1938	Michael E. Stone	1965	1965	2007	British-Israeli professor emeritus of Armenian Studies and of Comparative Religion	
1938	John D. Turner	1965	1970	2017	American the Cotner Professor of Religious Studies and Charles J. Mach University Professor of Classics and History Classics & Religious Studies	1938-2019

1938	Elizabeth A. Clark	1965	1965	2014 w	American the John Carlisle Kilgo Professorship of Religion at Duke University	
1938	Mary Esther Kropp Dakubu	1966	1968	2016 w	Ghanaian linguist	1938-2016
1938	Charles Laughlin	1966	1972	2003	Canadian neuroanthropologist known primarily for having co-founded a school of neuroanthropological theory called "biogenetic structuralism."	
1938	Napoleon Chagnon	1966	1966	1999	American anthropologist, professor of anthropology	1938-2019
1938	Diskin William Clay	1966	1967	2008	American scholar of Classics	1938-2014
1938	William Berg	1966	1966	2005	American classicist	
1938	Henk Verkuyl	1967	1972	2012	Dutch linguist	
1938	Paul Chapin	1967	1967	2003	American linguist	1938-2015
1938	Gerald James Larson	1967	1967	1999	American Indologist known for his writings on yoga	1938-2019
1938	Leonard H. Lesko	1967	1969	2005	American Chairman of the Department of Egyptology at Brown University	
1938	Reidar Grønhaug	1967	1975	2005	Norwegian social anthropologist.	1938-2005
1938	Alan Walker	1967	1967	2010	British the Evan Pugh Professor of Biological Anthropology and Biology	1938-2017
1938	Una Canger	1968	1968	2008 w	Danish linguist	
1938	Anna Seidel	1968	1968	1991 w	German Sinologist who was regarded as an authority in the study of Taoism	1938-1991
1938	Christopher Robert Hallpike	1968	1968	1998	British-Canadian anthropologist	
1938	Melvyn Goldstein	1968	1968	2009	American social anthropologist and Tibet scholar	
1938	Robin Cormack	1968	1968	2004	British classicist and art historian, specialising in Byzantine art	
1938	Jean Aitchison	1969		2003 w	British Professor of Language and Communication	
1938	Anthony C. Yu	1969	1969	2006	Hong Kong-American scholar of literature and religion, eastern and western	1938-2015
1938	Samir Khalil Samir	1969		2015	Egyptian Jesuit priest, Islamic scholar, Orientalist, and Catholic theologian	
1938	Jack Chambers	1970	1970	2005	Canadian linguist (sociolinguistics)	
1938	Rostislav Rybakov	1970	1981	2009	Russian scholar of Oriental Studies, writer, Indologist	
1938	Klaus Döring	1970	1970	2003	German classical philologist and philosophical historian	

1938	John Swales	1971	No	2007	British Linguist
1938	Hans Henrich Hock	1971	1971	2007	American Professor Emeritus of Linguistics and Sanskrit
1938	William J. Higginson	1971	No	2008	American poet, translator and author most notable for his work with haiku and renku
1938	Claude Buridant	1971		2004	French linguist, professor emeritus of French and Romance philology
1938	Suka Hardjana	1972		2004	w Indonesian musician, pedagog, thinker, and music writer
1938	David B. Zilberman	1972	1972	1977	Ukrainian-American philosopher and sociologist, scholar of Indian philosophy and culture
1938	Andrew Turton	1972	1976	2000	British anthropologist, specialised on Thailand and the Tai peoples of Southeast Asia
1938	Edward Barna Kurjack	1972	1972	2006	American Mayan anthropologist who was known for his contributions to the study of Mayan settlement patterns and society
1938	Лилия Шарифовна Вильчек	1973	1973	2009	w Russian literature critic
1938	Sally McConnell-Ginet	1973	1973	2010	w American Professor Emerita of Linguistics (language of gender and sexuality)
1938	Serena Nanda	1973	1973	2010	w American author, anthropologist, and professor emeritus
1938	Roger Corless	1973	1973	2000	British Professor of Religion
1938	William Lancaster	1974	1974	2005	British social anthropologist who has specialised in the study of the Arab world, particularly the bedouin tribes in the Levant and Middle East
1938	Dina Dahbany-Miraglia	1975	1983	2003	w American-Yemени linguistic anthropologist
1938	Svein Bjerke	1975	1975	2006	Norwegian religious historian and professor
1938	Ekkehart Malotki	1976	1978	2004	German-American linguist (Hopi language and culture)
1938	Ian Keen	1978	1979	2002	Australian anthropologist, whose research interests cover Yolngu kinship structures and religion, Aboriginal land rights and economies, and language
1939	Thomas G. Bever	1961	1967	2004	American Professor of Psychology, Linguistics, Cognitive Science, and Neuroscience
1939	Murray Leaf	1961	1966		American social and cultural anthropologist

1939	Erich Zenger	1961	1961	2004	German Roman Catholic priest and theologian	1939-2010
1939	Georgios Babiniotis	1962	1962	2012	Greek linguist and philologist and former Minister of Education and Religious Affairs of Greece	
1939	John C. Wells	1962	1971	2006	British linguist (phonetics, Esperanto)	
1939	Wolfgang U. Dressler	1962	1962	2004	Austrian linguist-polyglot	
1939	Michael Clyne	1962	1965	2005	Australian linguist, academic and intellectual	1939-2010
1939	Burkhard Gladigow	1962	1962	2004	German scholar of religious studies and classical philology	
1939	Maurice Bloch	1963	1967	2016	British anthropologist (relating social anthropology to linguistics and cognitive psychology)	
1939	Robert M. W. Dixon	1963	1991	2004	Australian linguist (syntax, typology, Australian languages, Amazonian languages)	
1939	Gérard Diffloth	1963	1968	2004	American Professor of linguistics	
1939	Daniel Cazés	1963		2008	Mexican anthropologist and gender studies scholar	1939-2012
1939	Neilson Smith	1964	1964	2006	British linguist (syntax, language acquisition)	
1939	Yorick Wilks	1964	1968	2007	British computer scientist (artificial intelligence, computational linguistics, natural language processing, semantics)	
1939	Nik Safiah Karim	1964		2003 w	Malaysian Malay language grammarian	
1939	Elizabeth C. Traugott	1964	1964	2004 w	American linguist (grammaticalization, subjectification, and constructionalization)	
1939	Dan Slobin	1964	1964	2015	American Professor Emeritus of psychology and linguistics	
1939	Epeli Hau'ofa	1964	1975	2009	Tongan (Papua NG) and Fijian writer and anthropologist	1939-2009
1939	Paul Mellars	1964	1977	2006	British academic, archaeologist and pre-historian	
1939	Thomas McEvilley	1964	1968	2008	American art critic, poet, novelist, and scholar	1939-2013
1939	Johann Hüttner	1964	1964	2004	Austrian theatre studies scholar, Germanist	
1939	Myles Burnyeat	1964		2006	British English scholar of ancient philosophy	1939-2019
1939	Marilyn Vihman	1965	1971	2004 w	British Professor of Language and Linguistic Science	
1939	Max Coltheart	1965	1965	2009	Australian cognitive scientist	
1939	Răzvan Theodorescu	1965	1972		Romanian art historian, historian and politician	
1939	Wolfgang Raible	1965	1965	2007	German linguist (Romance studies, general linguistics)	
1939	Egil Kraggerud	1965	1968	2002	Norwegian philologist	

1939 Paul J. Hopper	1965	1967		British-American linguist	
1939 Richard W. Bailey	1965	1965	2011	American linguist, scholar of the English language	1939-2011
1939 Victor Golla	1965	1970	2007	American linguist and a leading expert on the indigenous languages	
1939 Michael J. Mikos	1965	1977	2001	Polish-American professor of foreign languages and literature (Polish language, literature, and culture)	
1939 Anthony Traill	1965		2005	South African linguist (specifically a phonetician)	1939-2007
1939 Oliver Rackham	1965	1973	2006	British academic at the University of Cambridge who studied the ecology, management and development of the British countryside, especially trees, woodlands and wood pasture	1939-2015
1939 Lorenzo Renzi	1965	1983	2012	Italian linguist and philologist	
1939 Neil Hollander	1966	1970	2017	American writer, film director and producer, journalist and sailor	
1939 Tomasz P. Krzeszowski	1966	1966		Polish English language educator, linguist (Contrasting Languages)	
1939 Jane H. Hill	1966	1966	2009 w	American anthropologist and linguist	
1939 A. Roberto Frisancho	1966	1969	2008	Peruvian biological anthropologist and the Arthur F. Thurnau Professor of Anthropology	
1939 Claudio Magris	1966	1966	2006	Italian scholar, translator and writer	
1939 Bernd Heine	1967	1967	2012	German linguist and specialist in African studies	
1939 Bernhard Gröschel	1967	1967		German linguist and slavist (Slavic Studies, General Linguistics, Phonetics and Communication Studies)	1939-2009
1939 Pádraig Ó Riain	1967		2004	Irish Celticist and prominent hagiologist focusing on Irish hagiography, martyrdom, mythology, onomastics and codicology	
1939 Jean François Billeter	1967	1976	1999	Swiss sinologist and honorary professor	
1939 Jerzy Bartmiński	1967	1971	2011	Polish linguist and ethnologist	
1939 Alfonso Ortiz	1967	1967	1997	American Native American cultural anthropologist	1939-1997
1939 Josip Bratulić	1968	1968	2002	Croatian philologist and a historian of literature and culture	
1939 Sarah Thomason	1968	1968	2013 w	American scholar of linguistics	
1939 Jaleh Amouzgar	1968	1968	2005 w	Iranian Iranist	
1939 Stig Johansson	1968	1968	2008	Swedish-Norwegian linguist	1939-2010

1939	Dennis Tedlock	1968	1968	2007	American the McNulty Professor of English and Research Professor of Anthropology	1939-2016
1939	Gail Lee Bernstein	1968	1968	2007	American Professor Emerita of History (history of Japanese women, and is considered one of the pioneers in this field)	
1939	Evelyn Rawski	1968	1968	2004	American Distinguished University Professor in the Department of History of the University of Pittsburgh and a scholar in Chinese and Inner Asian history	
1939	Helene Hagan	1968	1983	2010 w	Moroccan-American anthropologist and Amazigh activist	
1939	Néstor García Canclini	1968	1975	2007	Argentinean academic and anthropologist known for his theorization of the concept of "hybridity"	
1939	Jean Lave	1968	1968	2006 w	American cultural anthropologist	
1939	NJ. Allen	1969	1976	2002	British social anthropologist (Himalayi)	
1939	Vincent Crapanzano	1969	1970	2013	American Distinguished Professor of Anthropology and Comparative Literature at the Graduate Center of the City University of New York	
1939	Gottfried Adam	1969	1969	2006	German evangelical theologian	
1939	Annabel Cormack	1970	1989	2004 w	British UCL linguistics	
1939	Itamar Even-Zohar	1970	1972	2009	Israeli culture researche and translator	
1939	Shirley Brice Heath	1970	1970	2010 w	American linguistic anthropologist (Professor of English and Dramatic Literature and Linguistics)	
1939	Ніна Клименко	1970	1970	2018 w	Ukrainian liguist	
1939	John Asher Dunn	1970	1970	2000	American linguist	
1939	Jamal Badawi	1970		2005	Egyptian-Canadian professor, author, preacher and speaker on Islam	
1939	Carmen Bernand	1970	1970	2005 w	French historian and anthropologist	
1939	David MacDougall	1970	No	2014	American visual anthropologist, academic, and documentary filmmaker, who is known for his ethnographic film work in Africa, Australia and India	
1939	Arvo Krikmann	1971	1975	2014	Estonian academician, folklorist, linguist, paremiologist, and humour researcher	
1939	Moshe Bar-Asher	1971	1976	2009	Israeli President of the Academy oh Hebrew Language	
1939	Edith A. Moravcsik	1971	1971	2009 w	Hungarian-American linguist	

1939 Julius Lester	1971		2003	American (African) writer of books for children and adults and an academic
1939 Heinz Schlaffer	1971	1971	2004	German Germanist and Professor of Literary Science
1939 Karin Aijmer	1972	1972	2015 w	Swedish linguist
1939 Jorgo Bulo	1972	1982	2015	Albanian philologist, historian, and literary critic
1939 E. F. K. Koerner	1972	1972	2001	Polish-American author, researcher, professor of linguistics, and historian of linguistics
1939 Marilyn Jensen Houlberg	1973	1973	2007 w	American leading expert on the arts and culture of Haitian Vodou
1939 Giulio Angioni	1973		2013	Italian writer and anthropologist
1939 Lucy Seki	1973	1973	2010 w	Brazilian linguist specializing in indigenous languages of the Americas
1939 John H. Moore	1974	1974	2010	American Professor and Chair of the Anthropology Department at the University of Florida
1939 Anna Parzymies	1976	1976	2009 w	Polish arabist, doctor of oriental studies, and professor
1939 George Saliba	1977		2005	American Professor of Arabic and Islamic Science at the Department of Middle Eastern, South Asian, and African Studies
1939 Knud Lambrecht	1979	1986	2010	German Professor Emeritus of French Linguistics
1939 Kari Vogt	1982		w	Norwegian religious historian